

Design and Implementation of a Circular Patch Antenna for 2.4 GHz IoT Applications Using CST

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Abstract – This work addresses the comprehensive development of a microstrip radiator on an FR-4 substrate, intended for operation within the Industrial, Scientific, and Medical (ISM) band. The methodology spanned from the theoretical calculation of geometric parameters to electromagnetic validation using CST Studio Suite software, culminating in the prototype manufacturing. Experimental measurements, conducted with a Vector Network Analyzer (VNA), reported a resonant frequency of 2.397 GHz and a VSWR of 1.33, demonstrating optimal impedance matching. Furthermore, spectral analysis tests confirmed the design's directivity with an 18 dB aligned-to-misaligned signal difference and validated the reciprocity theorem in a real-world link, proving the device's viability for sensor nodes in Wi-Fi and Zigbee networks.

Keywords— ISM band, IoT, circular patch antenna, CST Studio Suite, VSWR, reciprocity.

I. INTRODUCTION

The global communications infrastructure has undergone a drastic change due to the massive deployment of interconnected nodes, demanding increasingly efficient hardware to sustain the growth of sensor networks and smart devices [1], [2]. Within this ecosystem, the 2.4 GHz ISM band remains the fundamental spectrum for the operation of short-range, low-power protocols such as Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, and Zigbee [3]–[6]. However, the saturation of this band and the need to reduce manufacturing costs impose severe restrictions on the design of radio frequency components, which must guarantee robust performance without increasing the final device budget.

Microstrip antennas respond to these needs thanks to their low profile and integration capability into printed circuit boards (PCBs) [7]. Despite their mechanical advantages, their implementation on economical substrates with high dielectric losses, such as FR-4, introduces significant technical challenges that degrade radiation efficiency and bandwidth if rigorous electromagnetic modeling is not performed.

This research proposes and validates a design methodology for printed radiators that prioritizes local manufacturing viability. Unlike implementations evaluating complete telecommunications systems, this work isolates the radiating component to contrast discrepancies between the simulated theoretical model and real physical behavior. The purpose is to determine whether a geometric design optimized on standard materials can meet the strict impedance matching and directivity requirements necessary to establish stable wireless links.

II. DESIGN METHODOLOGY

A. Specification and Selection of Materials

The design was oriented to cover the 2.4 GHz ISM band, whose range assigned by the ITU is from 2.400 to 2.4835 GHz [8], requiring a minimum bandwidth of 83.5 MHz to support standard Wi-Fi and Zigbee channels [9]. A circular patch topology fed by a microstrip line with inset was selected to achieve a precise 50Ω match.

For the substrate, FR-4 (Flame Retardant-4) composite material was chosen due to its low cost and availability in the local market, despite its moderate dielectric losses [10]. The physical and electrical parameters of the base material are detailed in Table I.

TABLE I
SUBSTRATE AND DESIGN PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value	Description
ϵ_r	4.4	Dielectric constant (FR-4)
h	1.5 mm	Substrate height
t	0.035 mm	Copper thickness (1 oz)
f_r	2.4 GHz	Target center frequency

B. Geometric Sizing

The geometry of the antenna and its main design parameters are illustrated in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Geometric schematic of the circular patch antenna with inset feed, defining the design variables (a , S_g , S_i , L_f , W_f , L_g , W_g)

The dimensions of the radiating element were determined using the standard resonant cavity model for the dominant TM_{110} mode proposed by Balanis [7].

First, an auxiliary factor (F) is calculated, which depends on the target resonant frequency (f_r in Hz), the substrate height (h in cm) and the relative dielectric constant (ϵ_r):

$$F = \frac{8.791 \times 10^9}{f_r \sqrt{\epsilon_r}} \quad (1)$$

Subsequently, the physical radius of the patch (a , in cm) is determined by correcting this F factor to compensate for the fringing fields effect, using the constitutive expression:

$$a = \frac{F}{\left[1 + \frac{2h}{\pi \epsilon_r F} \left(\ln \frac{\pi F}{2h} + 1.7726\right)\right]^{1/2}} \quad (2)$$

Substituting the design values ($f_r = 2.4 \times 10^9$ Hz, $h = 0.15$ cm, $\epsilon_r = 4.4$), a theoretical radius of $a = 1.763$ cm was obtained.

For the dimensioning of the ground plane ($L_g \times W_g$), the design criterion to minimize edge diffraction effects was applied, ensuring that the metallic structure exceeds the patch dimensions by at least six times the substrate height [7]:

$$L_g > 2(a + 6h) \quad (3)$$

$$W_g > 2(a + 6h) \quad (4)$$

Following this restriction, final dimensions of 86.70 mm \times 69.07 mm were selected.

On the other hand, the width of the feed line (W_f), necessary to obtain a characteristic impedance of $Z_0 = 50\Omega$, was determined using the analytical synthesis equations for microstrip. Given that a width-to-height ratio $W_f/h < 2$, was anticipated, the standard approximation proposed by Pozar [10] was employed:

$$W_f = \frac{8h\epsilon^A}{e^{2A} - 2} \quad (5)$$

Where the auxiliary coefficient A incorporates the material properties and the target impedance:

$$A = \frac{Z_0}{60} \sqrt{\frac{\epsilon_r + 1}{2}} + \frac{\epsilon_r - 1}{\epsilon_r + 1} \left(0.23 + \frac{0.11}{\epsilon_r}\right) \quad (6)$$

Substituting the FR-4 parameters ($\epsilon_r = 4.4$, $h = 1.5$ mm y $Z_0 = 50\Omega$), a theoretical width of 2.82 mm was obtained, which was implemented in the simulation.

C. Simulation Setup

Electromagnetic modeling was performed in CST Studio Suite software using the Time Domain Solver (FIT). A computational domain with open boundary conditions (Open (add space)) was defined in all directions to emulate free space. The excitation was configured using a Waveguide Port assigned to the lateral face of the substrate and the feed line, with adaptive meshing to ensure S-parameter convergence in the 2 to 3 GHz range.

Due to the mesh cell restrictions inherent to the educational license of the software, an optimized local meshing strategy was applied, concentrating the calculation density exclusively on the patch edges and the feed line to maintain result accuracy without exceeding the computational limit. The final configuration of the computational model, detailing the radiator geometry and the excitation port location, is presented in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Three-dimensional model of the antenna in CST Studio Suite, visualizing the circular patch with inset feed, the dielectric substrate, and the waveguide port assignment at the bottom edge.

III. IMPLEMENTATION AND EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

A. Prototype Fabrication

Based on the optimized model, the antenna prototype was fabricated using standard printed circuit board (PCB) manufacturing techniques on the previously characterized FR-4 laminate. Given that the simulation platform used had limitations for direct export of manufacturing files, the final geometry was replicated in Advanced Design System (ADS) to generate the Gerber files required for the local chemical photo-etching process.

The metallized pattern transfer process was performed via chemical photo-etching to guarantee the dimensional fidelity of the feed slot (inset), which is critical for impedance matching.

For the connection interface, 50 Ω SMA male (Sub-Miniature Version A) connectors were installed in an edge-mount configuration. This gender configuration was chosen to facilitate direct coupling with the female interface of the available test bench, ensuring a robust mechanical and electrical transition. The soldering of the center pin to the microstrip line and the casing to the ground plane was performed manually, paying special attention to minimizing excess solder that could introduce parasitic capacitances.

Fig. 3. Fabricated prototype of the circular patch antenna with soldered male SMA connector.

B. Measurement Setup

The experimental validation was structured in two phases to characterize both network parameters and radiation performance.

1) Impedance Measurement: A portable Vector Network Analyzer (VNA), model NanoVNA V2, was employed. After applying a SOLT (Short-Open-Load-Through) calibration protocol to eliminate systematic errors, the prototype was connected to port 1 of the instrument. The objective was to record the reflection coefficient (S_{11}) and visualize the complex input impedance on the Smith Chart, thereby verifying resonance and the load type (inductive/capacitive) in the band of interest [11].

2) Transmission and Link Tests: A test bench composed of an RF signal generator and a Rohde & Schwarz FSH4 portable spectrum analyzer was configured [12]. The measurement procedure consisted of three stages:

- Reference: Measurement of the ambient noise floor with no antennas connected to establish the minimum detection threshold.
- Direct Link: Configuration of the fabricated patch antenna as the transmitter (Tx) connected to the generator, and a broadband omnidirectional telescopic antenna as the receiver (Rx) at the analyzer, separated by a fixed distance in the far-field zone.
- Reciprocity: Role reversal, connecting the telescopic antenna to the generator (Tx) and the patch antenna to the analyzer (Rx), in order to validate the Reciprocity Theorem and the prototype's sensitivity as a receiver.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section details the comparative analysis between the simulated model and the fabricated prototype. Impedance parameters, resonant behavior, and performance in a real radiocommunication link are evaluated.

A. Electromagnetic Simulation Analysis

The simulation in CST Studio Suite allowed predicting the far-field behavior of the antenna prior to its fabrication.

Fig. 4. Simulated far-field radiation pattern (3D), showing directivity perpendicular to the patch surface.

As observed in Fig. 4, the simulated radiation pattern exhibits a directional pattern perpendicular to the patch surface, characteristic of microstrip antennas operating in their fundamental mode. The highest energy concentration is oriented along the positive z-axis (main lobe), while back radiation is mitigated by the ground plane.

B. Impedance Characterization

For the experimental validation of S-parameters, the previously calibrated NanoVNA was employed.

Fig. 5. Verification of VNA calibration using a standard 50Ω load (SWR ≈ 1.00).

Fig. 5 confirms the successful calibration of the instrument. Subsequently, the fabricated antenna was connected to analyze its complex impedance.

Fig. 6. Input impedance measured on the Smith Chart, showing the resonance loop centered at 2.398 GHz.

In Fig. 6, the impedance trace crosses the real axis near the normalized center of the Smith Chart, evidencing satisfactory matching and minimized reactive part at the operating frequency.

Fig. 7. Measurement of the Voltage Standing Wave Ratio (VSWR) of 1.33 at the resonant frequency.

The quantitative analysis of the matching is presented in Fig. 7. A value of VSWR = 1.33 was obtained at the frequency of 2.397 GHz. This result is highly satisfactory (VSWR < 2.0), although a slight frequency shift relative to the theoretical 2.4 GHz (approx. 3 MHz) is observed, attributable to tolerances in the dielectric permittivity of the FR-4 substrate.

C. Link Tests and Spectral Analysis

To verify performance in a real-world scenario, received power measurements were conducted using the spectrum analyzer.

Fig. 8. Noise floor level of the spectrum analyzer with no antenna connected (≈ -92 dBm).

Fig. 8 establishes the environmental noise baseline at approximately -92 dBm. When transmitting with the patch antenna misaligned with respect to the receiver, a power of -85 dBm is recorded (Fig. 9), confirming the antenna's ability to attenuate signals off the main axis.

Fig. 9. Received power spectrum with antennas misaligned off the main axis (≈ -85 dBm).

Conversely, when correctly aligning both antennas (boresight), the received power increases drastically to -67 dBm (Fig. 10). This 18 dB difference experimentally validates the high directivity of the design.

Fig. 10. Received power spectrum in direct alignment condition (Boresight) (≈ -67 dBm).

Finally, the configuration was reversed (reciprocity test) using the patch antenna as a receiver. A maximum power of -68 dBm was recorded (Fig. 11), a value almost identical to the previous case, validating the Reciprocity Theorem and the prototype's sensitivity.

Fig. 11. Reception spectrum using the patch antenna as receiver, reaching a maximum power of -68 dBm.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Following the development of the design, simulation, and experimental validation of the prototype, the following conclusions are established:

- A circular patch antenna was successfully implemented with an experimental resonant frequency of 2.397 GHz and a VSWR of 1.33. These values validate the accuracy of the theoretical design equations used for the patch geometry on FR-4 substrate, remaining within the acceptable operating range ($VSWR < 2$).

- Spectral tests demonstrated an 18 dB difference in received power between the direct alignment condition and the misaligned condition. This finding experimentally confirms that the antenna possesses significant directivity perpendicular to its surface, minimizing interference from unwanted sources in the link.
- A slight frequency shift (3 MHz) was observed relative to the ideal design. It is concluded that this discrepancy is attributable to variations in the dielectric constant of commercial FR-4 substrate and parasitic effects from manual soldering, critical factors to consider in high-precision designs.
- In response to Internet of Things industry requirements, this work demonstrates that it is feasible to manufacture functional antennas for the 2.4 GHz band using low-cost materials and local manufacturing techniques. The confirmation of the Reciprocity Theorem in the prototype ensures its operability in both transmission and reception, validating its use in sensor nodes for Wi-Fi and Zigbee networks where hardware budget is a priority constraint.
- As lines for future research, the implementation of this radiating element in antenna arrays to increase the total system gain is proposed. Additionally, studying the impact of protective coatings (radomes) on input impedance is suggested to guarantee node durability in hostile outdoor environments.

REFERENCES

- [1] International Telecommunication Union, "Internet of Things reference model," ITU-T Y.2060, 2012.
- [2] Cisco Systems, "The Internet of Things, How the Next Evolution of the Internet Is Changing Everything," Cisco Internet Business Solutions Group (IBSG), 2011.
- [3] International Telecommunication Union, "Industrial, scientific and medical (ISM) applications," ITU-R SM.1056, 1994.
- [4] IEEE, "Wireless LAN Medium Access Control and Physical Layer Specifications," IEEE 802.11-2016, 2016.
- [5] Bluetooth SIG, "Bluetooth Core Specification," Bluetooth Specification v5.0, 2019.
- [6] IEEE, "Low-Rate Wireless Personal Area Networks," IEEE 802.15.4-2015, 2015.
- [7] C. A. Balanis, *Antenna Theory: Analysis and Design*, 4th ed. New York, NY, USA: Wiley, 2016.
- [8] International Telecommunication Union (ITU), "Recommendation ITU-R SM.1056-1: Industrial, scientific and medical (ISM) applications," Geneva, 1994.
- [9] IEEE Standards Association, "IEEE Standard for Information technology--Telecommunications and information exchange between systems Local and metropolitan area networks--Specific requirements - Part 11: Wireless LAN Medium Access Control (MAC) and Physical Layer (PHY) Specifications," IEEE Std 802.11-2016, pp. 1-3534, Dec. 2016.
- [10] D. M. Pozar, *Microwave Engineering*, 4th ed. Hoboken, NJ, USA: Wiley, 2011.

- [11] NanoRFE, "NanoVNA V2 Vector Network Analyzer User Manual," v1.3, 2020.
- [12] Rohde & Schwarz, "R&S FSH Handheld Spectrum Analyzer - Product Brochure," Munich, Germany, 2021.